

Coral Microbiome Harvesting and Transplantation: A Low-Tech “Coral Microbiome Transplantation (CMT)” Protocol for Reef Restoration Using Thermally Pre-Selected Donors

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Summary

Coral microbiome transplantation has been proposed by Doering et al. (2021) as a tool to support microbiome-assisted coral restoration by transferring microbial communities from donor colonies to recipient corals. This protocol describes a low-technology workflow for harvesting and transplanting coral-associated microbiomes without requiring microbial isolation, culturing, or prior taxonomic characterization. The protocol is adapted from previous coral microbiome transplantation approaches and is intended for use in restoration or experimental settings where donor colonies can be selected based on measured performance traits, such as thermal tolerance. Donor colonies may be prescreened using acute thermal assays, such as the Coral Bleaching Automated Stress System (CBASS), to identify colonies with comparatively high thermal tolerance. Recipient corals are subjected to a microbiome-depletion step before inoculation to increase niche availability and facilitate establishment of donor-associated microorganisms. Donor microbiomes are then harvested as a coral tissue slurry and used to inoculate recipient corals under controlled incubation conditions prior to outplanting or downstream experimental use. This protocol provides a standardized field-compatible procedure for coral microbiome harvesting and transfer. It is designed to reduce technical barriers associated with microbiome-based interventions while maintaining a structured workflow for donor selection, recipient preparation, inoculation, and post-treatment handling.

Overall objective

To provide a standardized, low-technology, field-applicable workflow for harvesting donor-derived microbiomes from thermally tolerant coral colonies and transferring them to recipient colonies for experimental or restoration-oriented assessment of microbiome-assisted heat-stress resilience.

Employed methods

1. Thermal pre-screening of a coral population of interest using short-term heat-stress assays, such as CBASS, to identify comparatively tolerant donor colonies and susceptible recipient colonies.
2. Collection of donor coral tissue using an airbrush to generate a donor-derived tissue slurry for microbiome harvesting.
3. Induction of mucus release in recipient corals by inverted air exposure to reduce existing surface-associated microbial niche occupancy before inoculation.
4. Incubation of recipient coral fragments in donor-derived, microbiome-enriched seawater to facilitate coral microbiome transplantation.

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Protocol

I. Thermal pre-screening to assign microbiome donor and recipient corals

Purpose

This step identifies candidate microbiome donor and recipient colonies based on colony-specific thermal tolerance. Coral colonies are screened using short-term heat-stress assays, such as CBASS, and ranked according to their ED50 values. Colonies with comparatively high ED50s are assigned as candidate microbiome donors, whereas colonies with comparatively low ED50s are assigned as candidate recipients. Please refer to references provided at the end of this protocol for further info.

Procedure

1. Select and sample coral colonies

- Select approximately 20 colonies per species to capture the distribution of thermal tolerance within the target population and to provide sufficient variation for assigning donor and recipient colonies.
- Colonies should either be tagged underwater for later resampling or sampled with enough material to support both thermal pre-screening and subsequent microbiome harvesting or transplantation.
- As a guide, collect four small fragments (2 cm² cores for bouldering, 3-4 cm branches for branching species) per colony for CBASS-based thermal tolerance assessment, plus additional medium-sized fragments for microbiome harvesting and outplanting. When sampling all material at the same time, it is also advised to label and keep the medium-sized fragments in the reef using a permeable cage or crate.

2. Perform short-term heat-stress assays

- Conduct CBASS or an equivalent short-term heat-stress assay following established protocols. Determine colony-specific ED50 values as standardized thermal tolerance thresholds.

3. Rank colonies by thermal tolerance

- Rank all screened colonies by ED50. Assign colonies with the highest ED50 values as candidate microbiome donors and colonies with the lowest ED50 values as candidate recipient colonies.

4. Define donor–recipient contrasts

- Where possible, select donor and recipient colonies that differ by at least 1°C in ED50. This threshold provides a practical guide for ensuring a clear thermal tolerance contrast between donor and recipient groups.

Notes

- For experimental applications, high-ED50 colonies may also be included as control recipients to test whether microbiome transplantation has different effects in comparatively tolerant versus susceptible corals.
- Assignment of high-ED50 colonies as microbiome donors is based on measured host performance and should be treated as a selection heuristic. A high thermal tolerance threshold does not, by itself, demonstrate that the associated microbiome causally contributes to coral heat tolerance. Whether donor-derived microbiomes from thermally tolerant colonies can enhance recipient performance is currently under active investigation.

II. Microbiome harvesting from donor colonies by airbrush-based tissue spraying

Purpose

Airbrush-based tissue spraying is used to harvest donor-derived microbiomes from high ED50-ranked coral fragments by removing the surface mucus layer and coral tissue into sterile-filtered seawater. This approach captures material from both mucus-associated and tissue-associated microbial compartments, requires limited equipment, can be performed under field or nursery conditions, and produces a microbiome-enriched slurry for subsequent coral microbiome transplantation.

Procedure

1. Select donor fragments

- Select donor fragments from colonies with the highest ED50 values. Record colony identity, ED50 rank, fragment size, and number of fragments used.

2. Spray donor tissue

- Using an airbrush gun and fitted with a barrier filter tip, spray the donor fragment surface into a sterile collection container. Continue until the surface mucus layer and most visible tissue have been removed from the skeleton.

3. Collect donor-derived slurry

- Collect the resulting tissue- and mucus-enriched into sterile seawater as donor microbiome inoculum (aim for 100 to 500 ml; can be adjusted by topping up with sterile seawater).

4. Pool donor-derived microbiome slurry

- Pool the donor-derived microbiome slurries from selected top-performing donor colonies; for example, the top 5 of 20 screened colonies. Record the total pooled volume.
- Maintain at ambient or ideally cooler temperature if feasible, as warming can rapidly alter bacterial community composition.

Notes

- Sterile seawater can be prepared by passing freshly collected seawater through a 0.22 μm filter. This reduces the background microbial load and may improve the relative effect of the donor-derived inoculum. If sterile filtration is not available under field conditions, this step can be omitted, and clean, freshly collected seawater can be used instead (e.g., water from above the reef, not from the shore)
- Consider standardizing the tissue-removal step, e.g. by maintaining the airbrush tip at consistent distance (1 cm) from the coral fragment and using pressurized air at consistent pressure (80 PSI)
- Instead of blasting with dry air, you can blast with sterile-filtered seawater: collecting tissue into a known concentration of medium can help to collect the sample.
- Donor-derived microbiome extracts should be processed consistently across colonies and treatments. The number of donor colonies, extraction method, fragment size, extract volume, pooling strategy, and time between extraction and recipient inoculation should be recorded.
- As an alternative to airbrush-based tissue spraying, donor tissue can be homogenized using sterile glass beads and vortex-assisted bead beating to generate a tissue-derived microbial slurry. This approach may recover tissue-associated microorganisms more efficiently, but it is more disruptive, may affect microbial cell integrity, and requires stricter standardization of homogenization time, bead type, sample volume, and processing intensity.

- As a further alternative, induced mucus release (“mucus milking”) can be used for donor microbiome collection. This approach is less disruptive and allows collection of mucus-associated microorganisms, although it may recover a narrower subset of the donor-associated microbiome compared with tissue-based harvesting methods.

III. “Mucus milking” of recipient corals to reduce surface-associated bacteria

Purpose

This step prepares recipient coral fragments for coral microbiome transplantation by inducing mucus release through inverted air exposure. Mucus release is expected to reduce the surface-associated microbial load of recipient fragments and thereby transiently increase niche availability for donor-derived microorganisms during subsequent inoculation. This procedure should be interpreted as a microbiome-depletion step rather than a complete microbiome reset.

Procedure

1. Prepare and label recipient fragments

- Transfer medium-sized recipient fragments into a large plastic box (5-10 L) with fresh seawater. Fragments should be labeled according to colony origin, ED50 rank, and treatment group. We use underwater paper attached with reusable cable ties for this purpose.
- To facilitate handling and avoid crowding, place no more than approximately 20 fragments per box.
- Attach each fragment securely to a rope using reusable cable ties or an equivalent attachment method (Figure 1).

2. Induce mucus release by inverted air exposure

- Suspend the ropes with attached coral fragments upside down in air for 15 minutes. Conduct this step in a shaded location (no direct sunlight) with stable ambient temperature, ideally not higher than 25–30°C.
- Ensure that mucus released from one fragment does not drip onto other fragments. Fragments should be positioned so that mucus drips downward and away from neighboring samples (Figure 1).

3. Facilitate mucus removal

- Gently move or tap the rope after approximately 3 minutes and again after approximately 12 minutes to promote mucus release.
- After 15 minutes, remove the fragments from the rope and place them into sterile seawater. Carefully move each fragment through the seawater to remove remaining attached mucus.

4. Maintain fragments until inoculation

- Keep recipient fragments in sterile seawater in large plastic boxes until further processing.
- Minimize the time between mucus removal and the next processing step.
- Avoid heating/sun exposure as much as possible.

Notes

- Sterile seawater can be prepared by passing freshly collected seawater through a 0.22 µm filter. This reduces the background microbial load and may reduce microbial load prior to subsequent transplantation. If sterile filtration is not available under field conditions, use clean, freshly collected seawater instead.
- The extent to which mucus milking reduces resident microbial load and increases donor microbiome establishment is currently unknown and under active investigation. It may vary among coral species, fragment sizes, environmental conditions, and handling duration.
- For experimental applications, consider including untreated control recipients to distinguish handling effects from donor microbiome effects.
- Consider HOBO loggers in the plastic boxes to trace temperature dynamics.

Figure 1. “Mucus milking” of recipient coral fragments. Recipient coral fragments are suspended upside down in air to induce mucus release prior to coral microbiome transplantation. (A) Labeled coral fragments attached to a line during inverted air exposure. (B) Close-up of a recipient fragment releasing mucus droplets. This procedure is intended to reduce the resident surface-associated microbiome before incubation with donor-derived microbiome inoculum. Note that reusable cable ties are specified in the protocol because they reduce direct tissue contact and minimize tissue damage compared with rubber bands.

IV. Coral microbiome transplantation (CMT) by incubation with donor-derived microbiome inoculum

Purpose

This step inoculates recipient coral fragments with a pooled donor-derived microbiome inoculum. The donor inoculum is generated from high ED50-ranked coral colonies and added to recipient fragments following “mucus milking” to promote contact between donor-derived microorganisms and available surface-associated niche space. This step exposes recipient coral fragments to coral donor-derived inoculum as a means of coral microbiome transplantation prior to outplanting or downstream experimental processing, adapted from the strategy described by Doering et al. (2021).

Procedure

1. Add microbiome inoculum from step II.4. to recipient fragments from step III.4.

- Gently mix the prepared donor-derived microbiome inoculum before use.
- Divide the inoculum evenly among the incubation boxes so that each box receives the same inoculum volume.
- After adding the inoculum, gently stir the seawater to distribute the inoculum throughout the box without mechanically damaging the coral fragments.

2. Incubate recipient fragments

- Incubate recipient fragments for 1 hour under ambient reef water temperature or maximum monthly mean temperature; minimize heat/direct sun exposure.

3. Outplanting of treated recipient fragments

- After incubation, transport recipient coral fragments to the outplanting site in labeled bags or containers filled with fresh reef seawater. Keep fragments shaded and at ambient reef temperature, or slightly cooler where feasible, during transport and handling.
- Following outplanting, photograph each outplanted fragment after attachment and record spatial information, such as nursery rack position, tile number, plot number, or GPS coordinates, depending on the outplanting setup.

Notes

- For experimental purposes, record the inoculum volume added to each incubation box, the number of recipient fragments per box, incubation duration, seawater volume, temperature, light intensity, and time between incubation and outplanting or further processing.
- For experimental purposes, record the identity, treatment, donor inoculum, recipient colony, ED50 rank, outplanting location, and attachment position for each fragment. Labels and field records should allow each fragment to be traced unambiguously from donor and recipient assignment through incubation and outplanting.
- Consider HOBO loggers in the plastic boxes to track temperature dynamics.

Figure 3. Workflow for coral microbiome transplantation based on thermal tolerance pre-screening. Candidate coral colonies are sampled, labeled, and thermally pre-screened using acute heat-stress assays, such as CBASS. Colony-specific ED50 values are used to rank colonies by thermal tolerance and assign high ED50-ranked colonies as candidate microbiome donors and low ED50-ranked colonies as candidate recipients (A-C). Donor-derived microbiome inoculum is generated from high ED50-ranked fragments by airbrush-based tissue spraying into sterile seawater, producing a microbiome-enriched slurry that is pooled across selected donor colonies (D). Recipient fragments are prepared by inverted air exposure-induced "mucus milking" to reduce resident surface-associated microbiomes before inoculation (E). Prepared recipient fragments are then incubated with the pooled donor-derived microbiome inoculum as a means of coral microbiome transplantation prior to outplanting or downstream experimental processing (F-G). For experimental research purposes, fragment identity, treatment assignment, donor and recipient origin, ED50 rank, incubation conditions, and outplanting position should be tracked throughout the workflow. Figure adjusted from ChatGPT based on a BioRender.com draft.

References & Resources

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CBASS Material list & assay protocols

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